

The Reality Of Using Digital Technology On The Development Of E-Tourism In The Kingdom Of Saudi Arabia

Haifa Hammoud Al-Shammari, Nancy Abdel-Maboad El-Sawy

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 01, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: December 31, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Digital Technology, Tourism, Kingdom Of Saudi Arabia</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4409216</p>	<p><i>Tourism is one of the economic sectors most capable of advancing comprehensive development, reducing poverty, promoting sustainable development and peace, and benefiting from tourism with 10% of the gross domestic product in the world, and it has a major impact on exports, job creation, investment, infrastructure development and social inclusion institutions. Highlighting the importance of digital technology and communication information to revitalize the tourism and e-commerce sector and its positive contribution to economic growth from the Kingdom's 2030 vision in the Kingdom the importance of studying :The possibility of the tourism sector turning to electronic tourism Understand the importance of digital technology systems for tourism</i></p>

1. Introduction

The future of digital tourism depends on the understanding of those responsible for the mentality of consumers. Modern technology has influenced the methods of planning travel, spending holidays that vary from age to age, dealing with each consumer / client separately, and trying to satisfy it, and we must draw, according to the behavior of the new consumer, the features of a future Digital tourism.

The digital transformation affects the behavior of consumers and tourism clients; The report, entitled "digital tourism with immersive technology", indicates that in 2019, more than 50% of travel apps were downloaded to book flights and hotel rooms. At the same time, e-commerce is expected to account for more than half of e-commerce by 2021, and accordingly, the future of digital tourism is closely linked to the digital consumer and e-marketing, and social media is behind the radical change in the travel and tourism industry; Through these modern technical media, the industry has changed by transferring information, so information about this or that tourist destination can be delivered to millions of people, and the comments available affect various social media applications in the travel and tourism industry 'Through which the services provided in this industry are improved, and modern social media has paved the way to reach customers easily, which has raised their loyalty rates for companies and the bodies that they deal with, and therefore there will be no impact or talk about the future of digital tourism without talking about tourism marketing , While this type of marketing was one of the major drivers of the emergence of digital tourism.promotion

Study limits: The tourism sector in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (consumers and investors)

Study methodology: The research depends on the descriptive analytical approach, the descriptive approach to clarify the concepts of the study and the analytical approach to data analysis and the results of the opinion poll

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia 2030 vision aims to reduce the Kingdom's dependence on oil, diversify the sources of the economy, as well as on developing public services sectors such as health, education and tourism by strengthening these areas, And the digital transformation has managed "in a few years to storm all fields, in light of successive technological developments and provided all the requirements of life in a smart phone, and tourism is one of the most important areas affected by this development. A vacation is planned, harnessing innovation and digital developments that provide tourism with opportunities to improve the integrated development of tourism, through tourism companies licensed by the Ministry of Tourism.

The e-commerce in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia comes in the advanced ranks among all the e-commerce markets around the world, and it is a result of the efforts made by the Saudi Arabia Kingdom government and the compensation of the volume of e-commerce in the Kingdom and the regulation of e-commerce operations and the protection of the rights of the Saudi consumer

(The main question of the study)

Purpose of the study :

Electronic trade :

It is the process of exchanging goods and services through an Electronic means or electronic broker, and the Internet is often the electronic broker. As defined by the Saudi Ministry of Trade and Investment as an activity of a special nature that the service provider and the consumer undertake in whole or in part - by electronic broker in order to sell products or provide advertising services or exchange their data (E-commerce system), While the World Trade Organization defines it as activities to produce, distribute, market, sell, or deliver goods and services to the buyer through electronic media (Elesawy, Ibrahim2003)

Digital Marketing: Digital marketing is defined as the strategies that are carried out on the internet to promote and manage marketing strategies in digital ecosystems

E-commerce features:

- 1 - All transactions are completed electronically
- 2- Lack of a direct relationship between the parties to the process
- 3- Affected by the law of e-commerce
- 4- Dealing with more than one source at the same time
- 5- Trade in data and documents

E-commerce requirements:

- 1- Improving the communication and information technology infrastructure
- 2- Create the legislative and regulatory environment
- 3- Improving the business climate
- 4- Developing the communications industry and working to increase competitions
- 5- Development of support services
- 6- Securing electronic payment methods
- 7- Development of human cadres
- 8-Community Awareness Development (Mohamed, Seraj2008)

(Table No. 1) shows the number of Internet users (per million people) in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from 2013-2017

2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
51,928,839	71,125,1835	89,868,7156	106,364,3741	167,616,865

(World Bank Data 16/16/2016)

The Kingdom's efforts to maximize the importance of electronic commerce:

- Issuing the law regulating e-commerce

Which aims to support and maximize the importance of electronic commerce and strengthen the confidence of the Saudis in this new purchasing pattern, in addition to protecting the consumer from all fraud, misinformation or deception.

- Launching the “Marouf” service for electronic stores

In order to build more trust between online stores and shoppers to facilitate online shopping

- Launching an electronic commercial registry issuance service

For all who wish to launch an electronic store and issue its own electronic commercial registry, registration through simple steps and following all instructions (E-commerce system)

E-commerce challenges:

Lack of experience in the Gulf market - weak turnout by investment companies - the views of traditional merchants and lack of support for e-commerce - the failure of government and banking sectors and logistical services - lack of real knowledge of the growth and size of the market - the preference of traditional markets especially by women to enjoy - the fear of employees from losing their jobs - Focus on technology by the dealer, not the producer - Lack of decision-makers in e-commerce (Eldrab.Mazen)

Digital Tourism:

Digital tourism is the use of digital tools to prepare, organize, control and enjoy the travel experience when doing Tourism.

These are the services provided by information and communications technology for the purpose of achieving and enhancing tourism and hotel services through various open and closed networks, based on the principles and foundations of electronic commerce, and our focus in this context is on digitization of transportation system and building digital tourism services related to the smart transport network that enables the tourist to benefit. Among these services is the system in various aspects, highlighting the digitization of transport and communication services, and enhancing its role in developing the tourism sector in the Kingdom (Bazazo.Ibrahim 2016)

According to the World Economic Forum, "In the next decade (from 2016 to 2025), digitization in the field of aviation, travel, and tourism is expected to generate an added value for the sector of \$ 305 billion, transfer \$ 100 billion from traditional poles to new competitors, and generate benefits With a value of \$ 700 billion for customers and society as a whole, by reducing the environmental impact, enhancing safety and security, and saving costs and time for consumers. In addition, the sector will witness a net transfer of existing jobs, offset in

part by creating skills-based job opportunities from the next generation inside and outside the travel system (weforum 2017)

Digital tourism challenges: Legislation and outdated regulations - fear of failure - lack of awareness - lack of cooperation and communication with relevant authorities - lack of technological know-how - lack of funding – (World Tourism Organization)

****The total tourist establishments in the Kingdom 2018 (72,389 establishments) (Mas center)**

(Table No.2) Total tourism spending (Mas center)

City	Incoming trips	Domestic trips
Hail	43 million riyals	782 million riyals
Medina	599 million riyals	5.3 billion riyals
Mecca	72 billion riyals	16.7 billion riyals
El baha	47 million riyals	1.4 billion riyals
eljouf	242 million riyals	641 million riyals
Northern borders	397 million riyals	329 million riyals
Qassim	190 million riyals	1.3 billion riyals
Tabuk	239 million riyals	1.2 billion riyals
Jazan	90 million riyals	2.6 billion riyals
asseer	362 million riyals	6.1 billion riyals
Najran	48million riyals	870million riyals

(Table No.3) Tourism Indicators in the Kingdom: 2018 (Mas center)

Types of tourism	Domestic trips	Tourist spending	Highest face
Cultural tourism	5.1 million trips	6.7 billion riyals	Medina 1.1 million trips
Medical Tourism	557 thousand trips	1.1 million riyals	Riyadh region 381 thousand trips
Business tourism	2.5 million trips	16.5 billion riyals	Riyadh Region 1.6 million trips
Sports tourism	151 thousand trips	134 million riyals	Riyadh region 63 thousand trips

Electronic systems and services used in the activity of tourism establishments 2018 (General Authority for Statistics)

The percentage of the use of tourism activities for social networking programs varied between each other, as there are activities in which the percentage reached 100% for social media programs such as passenger and rail transport activity, while we find that activities that do not use these programs may reach 91% as in the activity Providing food and drink and 80% as in the activity of renting means of transportation, and the percentage of using distinctive activities for tourism for electronic programs in each of the residence activities for visitors and passenger transport by rail, air transport and travel agencies ranged between 83- 100% in their use of electronic programs, except that There are other activities in which the rate of non-use of electronic programs reaches 83% as the activity of providing food and drink and 61% as in the land transport activity for passengers and other services distinguished for tourism, while it became clear that a large percentage of the activities of tourist establishments possess cloud data amounting to 100% to 83% as In the activity of providing food and drink and 64% in the land transport activity of passengers.

(Table No.4) Electronic systems and services used in the activity of tourism establishments 2018

The economic activity	Using social media programs	Cloud data	Using electronic programs
Residence for visitors	64%	85%	83%
Food and drink service activity	9%	17%	17%
Rail transport of passengers	100%	100%	100%
Passenger land transport	32%	36%	39%

Water transport of passengers	60%	66%	54%
Air transport of passengers	100%	100%	100%
Transportation rental	20%	49%	51%
Travel agencies and other reservation services	68%	76%	95%
Cultural activities	49%	45%	60%
Sports and leisure activities	61%	48%	52%
Other distinguished services for tourism	39%	40%	39%

General Authority for Statistics

Main Digital Marketing Techniques for Digital Tourism

Strategies Based on Search Marketing

Search Engine Optimization (SEO) Site design improvement (SEO) is an advanced advertising system that was destined to upgrade the outcomes in the positioning of web crawlers known as SERPs (Search Engine Pages Results). It has been distinguished that the exploration concentrates on SEO on advanced the travel industry, since clients who are keen on making the acquisition of a flights ticket or to get data about a vacationer goal, perform look on web indexes, for example, Google or Yahoo! so as to discover data (Palos-Sanchez .2018)

Search Engine Marketing (SEM) is the making of supported advertisements (known as paid list items) in the list items of the principle web crawlers, for example, Google, Bing or Yahoo (De Pelsmacker et al., 2018). For this situation, this kind of strategy likewise incorporates presentations and pennants that aggrieve clients as for their pursuit history. In this sense, this advanced showcasing procedure are enacted when a client scans for a watchword that the sponsor has picked as predefined (Saura. 2019)

Search Store Optimization (ASO) is carried out in the applications stores such as Google Play (Android) and App store (Apple). The ASO serves as App Store Optimization and is a technique that consists in optimizing the app information in the main application stores (Saura.2019)

Strategies Based on Digital Methodologies

Sentiment Analysis (SA) is a system that comprises of gathering data from audits and remarks just as feelings from sightseers and voyagers who visit a spot or who demand data through informal organizations. In this sense, assessment examination systems are fixated on the investigation of positive, negative and nonpartisan sentiments as for the dissected informational index. This arrangement of information can be a database removed from stages, for example, Booking, TripAdvisor or Google Maps, including likewise from lodging profiles and traveler goals on Twitter (Saura. 2020)

Textual Analysis (TA) is a technique that is being used for digital marketing. In this sense, the methodology and its development are carried out in the same way as sentiment analysis, that is, this technique applied to digital tourism and its main objective is to collect databases in which a textual analysis consisting of the identification of key factors related to a subject of study can be applied. Therefore, textual analysis is a qualitative analysis procedure in which various factors related to an event. (Saura .2019).

eWord of Mouth (eWOM). Customers face more extravagant data conditions than previously and utilize online social stages, including informal communication locales, web journals, social shopping networks, and buyer audit destinations, to convey sentiments about items, administrations and trade buy experiences, these procedures are additionally founded on the expansion of positive surveys so organizations attempt to recognize those positive remarks with respect to the item or administration offered and move these interests to the chiefs so they can execute the input made by the clients both, negative and positive, on advanced the travel industry items (Saura.2019)

Strategies Based on Social Media

Programmatic and Remarketing Advertising

Remarketing and programmatic advertising in the tourism sector are techniques that are specialized in pursuing users online with banners or creatives based on displays in which they offer tourism products and services. This technique of digital marketing in the tourism sector consists of these displays pursuing users in their main profiles on social networks while the users are surfing the Internet. When a user visits a website, digital businesses install cookies in the users' browsers giving information about their interest to the tourism sector and about the specific products and services they have searched for (Reyes-Menendez.2019).

Social Ads (SADS) Advertising on social media platforms within the tourism sector consists of the development of advertising strategies and creativities that will appear only on social networks such as Instagram, Facebook or Twitter. This strategy basically consists of the development of promoting strategies for tourist destinations and that can be images or videos. (Kim, H. 2019).

Strategies Based on Content Marketing

Located-Based Social Networks Social geolocation networks have become an important tool for digital marketing strategies in the tourism sector. These strategies consist in the creation of new public profiles in social

networks specialized in the tourism sector. These pages can be perfectly located by the users who use their smartphones during their trips as well as to obtain information prior to their trips (Palos-Sanchez. 2018).

Influencers Marketing (IM) Influencers have become a key element to launch advertising messages to a series of users that have heterogeneous characteristics. Users tend to follow influencers in specific industries. Therefore, companies in the digital sector base their strategies on identifying which are the influencers that can provide advertising services (Coates. 2019)

Strategies Based on Digital Trends

Augmented Reality (AR) has been recognized as one of the advances that can change the eventual fate of the travel industry segment in the computerized condition. Utilizing expanded reality vacationers or explorers can collaborate with the landmarks and spots they visit through their cell phones, which likewise makes conceivable a genuine cooperation between the spots visited by voyagers and the voyagers themselves (Tavakoli. 2019) On the off chance that we connect the advancement of enlarged reality to the expansion in the utilization of cell phones far and wide and the rates of increment regarding the travel industry at the worldwide level, increased the truth is merged as one of things to come patterns for the improvement of this industry in the computerized condition (Palos-Sanchez. 2018).

Virtual Reality (VR) is the creation of mobile applications that can interact between the real world and a digital world that is viewed on mobile phones, tablets or computers. In this case, VR is interesting as long as users can see parallel stories that happened in a tourist environment or imagining the reconstruction of a specific geographical area thanks to applications that develop these parallel realities. (DiVerdi. 2019)

360o Videos Recording videos in 360o allows an authentic opportunity for the digital tourism sector. This technology can be watched through the Internet or through a screen, those are new perspectives that until now the users could not enjoy.

Digital Neuromarketing (DN) is increasingly becoming a science that studies how the behavior of the human being is linked to the decisions made by his brain (Spence, C. 2019). In this way, neuromarketing studies the human brain to try to anticipate the decisions it makes. If we apply this theory to the digital sector methodologies such as eye tracking can be developed, in which specialized software identifies where a user is looking at a specific screen. This technique therefore pursues to identify in detail where a user looks when enjoy a specific content in a website (Reyes-Menendez. 2018). These analysis actions are very important if it is considered that users visit websites globally every day. If this data is well analyzed, patterns can be found that help to improve the design of web pages about tourism or even improve the experiences that are offered through them as for example the improvement of the spaces destined to the experiences or the physical design of tourist gift shops or the improvement of the tourist offer in any type of channel or advertising support (Saura. 2020)

Internet of Things (IoT) has set up itself as a pattern far and wide. Progressively, there are gadgets associated with the Internet that gather information day by day. This information is put away so it very well may be organized by supervisors and can hence create ends dependent on their examination.

The vacationer condition is a lot of these associated gadgets and furthermore are progressively present in the travel industry segment since they can assist explorers with discovering destinations and spots with traveler intrigue or even assistance them to discover data. One of the patterns in the computerized the travel industry condition is the proposal of exercises and trips with this kind of gadgets that increase the value of the travel industry items offered through the Internet and are a key component for the advancement of systems connected to DMB ((Saura. 2020)

Business Intelligence (BI) is a reality in terms of the collection and analysis of massive data that comes mainly from the Internet. BI is considered a trend within the tourism sector because, although the collection of data is a reality, the useful and cost-effective analysis of these data must still be defined to be more effective (Richards, G.2019).The BI is consolidated as a process to obtain real information but there are opportunities that have not yet been defined correctly to make decisions in the tourism sector. In addition, in recent years BI strategies have applied different methodological approaches based on data mining and machine-learning, both techniques from the evolution and development of artificial intelligence. The application of these new techniques for the analysis of BI data has led to the increase of measurement strategies to obtain greater profitability within the BI and the companies that apply these measurement models (Chen. 2012).

Research Methodology :

- To discuss the questions, a field study was prepared by preparing data collection tools (demographic characteristics and survey forms) to measure the extent of support that digital technology directs to the tourism sector in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia according to the Kingdom's Vision 2030 according to those working in the field of digital tourism and e-commerce and also according to the views of those who benefit from those Companies.
- As one of the fields of descriptive studies, the target community was identified, and in the first stage, tourism companies in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and a questionnaire was conducted on 105 companies from the tourism sector in the Kingdom,
- In the second stage, a poll was conducted for a number of 495 heads of Saudi families in the Hail region
- The first questionnaire (for companies) was prepared, including some demographic characteristics of companies, in addition to two axes from the administrative point of view (12 items) and from the technical side (11 items) to measure the level of tourism companies' practice of digital technology, and the second questionnaire (for families benefiting from digital technology) was prepared In the field of tourism) including the demographic characteristics of the beneficiaries in addition to the two axes of electronic tourism (11 items) electronic marketing (11 items) and a five-level Likert scale was used and all statistical transactions were performed using the ver23 spss program.
- The validity of the questionnaires was confirmed by the validity of the internal consistency by calculating the Pearson correlation coefficient between the degree of each phrase and the axis to which it belongs. The reliability of the internal consistency of the questionnaires was validated, and the stability of the tools was calculated using the alpha-Crow Nebach coefficient, whose value was for the number of expressions of the first questionnaire - the first axis (12 phrases), the coefficient of 0.874 and the second axis (11 phrases) 0.919, which is a statistically acceptable value 0.01 as was Calculate the stability of the tools for the second questionnaire using the Alfa Crow Nebach coefficient, whose value for the first axis statements (11 phrases) is 0.896 coefficient and the second axis phrases (11 words) 0.856, which is a statistically acceptable value.
- Statistical analysis of the results of the questionnaire was performed, using coefficients (frequencies and percentage - t test - anova analysis).

Results and Discussion:

First: Analysis and interpretation of demographic characteristics according to the sample of the

Figure.1first study (tourist companies)

It is clear from the shapes that the number of companies by 36% did not exist in the areas most affected by digital developments, while 28% of the companies were in the capital, while 24% of the companies were in the coastal regions of the Kingdom, and this shows the extent of diversity in the companies under study, as well as The figure shows the diversity of the experiences of the companies under study, as the companies diversified from experiences of less than five years by 32% and companies with 5 years or more experience and ten years or more by 34% alike, as well as the diversity of services provided by tourist companies from ticket reservations and hotel and program reservations

(Figure.2) . Tourism and leisure trips, the percentage of companies that support all services is 62%.

advertising, as well as the diversity of the marketing systems of companies with reduced prices, individual programs, tourist groups, etc., as the activities of these companies vary from global and local activities And those

(figure.3) companies diversified their activities by 66%.

It is clear from the previous drawing the diversity of the offers offered by the companies under study, where the percentage of companies with diversity in the rate of offers reaches 52%, and all companies prefer to deal with customers without an intermediary, and 66% of the total companies are happy to evaluate the services provided by them by customers By 66%.

- Results in light of the study:

Table5 ANOVA TEST Depending on the location of the company

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Administrative	Between Groups	232.604	4	58.151	1.065	.378
	Within Groups	5188.556	95	54.616		
	Total	5421.160	99			
Technology	Between Groups	443.783	4	110.946	1.899	.117
	Within Groups	5549.857	95	58.420		
	Total	5993.640	99			
Electronic tourism	Between Groups	932.414	4	233.103	1.196	.318
	Within Groups	18515.746	95	194.903		
	Total	19448.160	99			

- From the table it is clear that there are no statistically significant differences between the different companies' responses to the questionnaire according to Due to the difference in the location of the company, the company's location did not affect the companies responses to digital tourism, whether administrative or technical, and this indicates the general policy during which tourism works in the Kingdom. Where all companies operate according to one system, which is the Kingdom's tourism system

Table .6 ANOVA TEST Depending on years of experience

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Administrative	Between Groups	338.131	2	169.065	3.226	.044
	Within Groups	5083.029	97	52.402		
	Total	5421.160	99			
Technology	Between Groups	139.787	2	69.894	1.158	.318
	Within Groups	5853.853	97	60.349		
	Total	5993.640	99			
Electronic tourism	Between Groups	552.395	2	276.198	1.418	.247
	Within Groups	18895.765	97	194.802		
	Total	19448.160	99			

- From the table it is clear that there are statistically significant differences at the level of 0.05 in terms of administration in favor of those with less than five years of experience, where the value of P3.266 is greater than its tabular counterpart and the average score of their responses reached 49.62, which is the highest compared to its counterparts and this shows The newly established companies in the Kingdom are trying hard to keep up with the recent developments in the tourism field for the more experienced companies as they work on the same charters since their inception, while there are no statistically significant differences between the responses of companies from the technical point of view or from the overall results of the e-tourism where the weakness of keeping up with Technological rapid developments in the field of tourism among companies owners.

Table.7 ANOVA TEST Depending on the services provided

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Administrative	Between Groups	362.857	4	90.714	1.704	.156
	Within Groups	5058.303	95	53.245		
	Total	5421.160	99			
Technology	Between Groups	783.740	4	195.935	3.573	.009
	Within Groups	5209.900	95	54.841		
	Total	5993.640	99			
Electronic tourism	Between Groups	2104.653	4	526.163	2.882	.027
	Within Groups	17343.507	95	182.563		
	Total	19448.160	99			

-It is clear from the table that there are no statistically significant differences between the responses of companies in terms of services provided administratively as they did not differ among them in terms of services due to the high level of administrative services throughout the Kingdom and the availability of a good experience component in the field of management, while there are statistically significant differences between The companies' responses in terms of services provided technically in favor of recreational activities at a level of 0.01, where the value of P 3.573 is greater than its tabular counterpart and their average responses reached 51.00 where differences appeared in the services provided technology according to the company's experience and the extent of its dealings with The consumer and the diversity of options are also statistically significant differences at the level of 0.05 in terms of services provided overall for e-tourism in favor of recreational activities where their average responses reached 107,00 and the value of P2,882 is greater than its tabular counterpart. As a result of enhancing the personal nature of the traveler and the consumer and employing modern technologies to activate the services provided

Table. 8 ANOVA TEST According to the marketing mechanism

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Administrative	Between Groups	548.970	4	137.242	2.676	.036
	Within Groups	4872.190	95	51.286		
	Total	5421.160	99			
Technology	Between Groups	370.735	4	92.684	1.566	.190

	Within Groups	5622.905	95	59.188		
	Total	5993.640	99			
Electronic tourism	Between Groups	1634.684	4	408.671	2.179	.077
	Within Groups	17813.476	95	187.510		
	Total	19448.160	99			

It is clear from the table that there are statistically significant differences between the responses of companies in terms of the marketing mechanism from an administrative point of view at the level of significance 0.05 in favor of the company representative, where the average of their responses reached 60.00 as the value of P2,676 is greater than its tabular counterpart and this indicates continuity In the usual and guaranteed mechanisms in terms of ensuring consumer attraction through direct persuasion through the delegate and the weakness of technological technologies such as augmented reality that supports consumer conviction in a technical way, while there are no statistically significant differences between the responses of companies depending on the mechanism of marketing from a technical point of view and on the whole from digital tourism.

Table .9ANOVA TEST According to the marketing system

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Administrative	Between Groups	562.293	3	187.431	3.703	.014
	Within Groups	4858.867	96	50.613		دال ٠,٠١
	Total	5421.160	99			
Technology	Between Groups	1239.562	3	413.187	8.344	.000
	Within Groups	4754.078	96	49.522		دال ٠,٠٠١
	Total	5993.640	99			
Electronic tourism	Between Groups	2267.749	3	755.916	4.224	.008
	Within Groups	17180.411	96	178.963		دال ٠,٠١
	Total	19448.160	99			

- It is clear from the table that there are statistically significant differences between the responses of companies from the administrative point of view in favor of tourist groups at the level of significance 0.01, where the average of their responses reached 51.00 and the value of P 3.703 was greater than their tabular counterpart, and there are also statistically significant differences between the responses of The company is technically in favor of tourism groups at the level of 0.001, where their average responses reached 47,00 and the calculated value of 8,344 is greater than its tabular counterpart, and there are statistically significant differences between the responses of companies from the total digital tourism in favor of tourist groups at The level of significance 0.01, where their average responses reached 98.50 and the calculated value of P 4,224, which is greater than its tabular counterpart. That is, as the tourism marketing system in the Kingdom depends on families, Saudi families and residents in the Kingdom

Table10ANOVA TEST Depending on the activities provided

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Administrative	Between Groups	581.485	2	290.742	5.827	.004
	Within Groups	4839.675	97	49.894		
	Total	5421.160	99			
Technology	Between Groups	374.662	2	187.331	3.234	.044
	Within Groups	5618.978	97	57.928		
	Total	5993.640	99			
Electronic tourism	Between Groups	1871.307	2	935.654	5.164	.007
	Within Groups	17576.853	97	181.205		
	Total	19448.160	99			

It is clear from the table that there are statistically significant differences at the level of 0.01 between the responses of companies from the administrative point of view according to the activities provided in favor of global activities, where the average of their responses reached 56,33 and the value of the calculated value of

5,827 is greater than its tabular counterpart, and there are differences with Statistical significance at the level of 0.05 between the responses of companies from the technical point of view according to the activities provided in favor of global activities with an average of 49.00 and a value of P 3,234 which is greater than its tabular counterpart, and there are statistically significant differences between the responses of the company's total digital tourism in favor of International companies at the level of significance 0.01, where their average responses were 105.33 and the value of P5,164 is higher than their tabular counterpart. Therefore, we conclude that Al-Olbia deals with international companies because there is a high degree of confidence and availability of means to complete the purchase.

Table .11ANOVA TEST Depending on the rate of offers

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Administrative	Between Groups	748.037	3	249.346	5.122	.002
	Within Groups	4673.123	96	48.678		
	Total	5421.160	99			
Technology	Between Groups	222.017	3	74.006	1.231	.303
	Within Groups	5771.623	96	60.121		
	Total	5993.640	99			
Electronic tourism	Between Groups	1725.660	3	575.220	3.116	.030
	Within Groups	17722.500	96	184.609		
	Total	19448.160	99			

It is clear from the table that there are statistically significant differences at the level of 0.01 between the responses of companies from the administrative point of view according to the rate of offers in favor of annual offers where the average of their responses reached 52.00 and the value of the calculated value of 5,122 is greater than its tabular counterpart, while there are no differences There is a statistically significant difference between the responses of companies from the technical point of view according to the rate of presentations presented, while there are statistically significant differences between the responses of the total companies for digital tourism according to the type of offers in favor of annual offers with an average of 98.25 and a value of P.3116 which is higher than its tabular counterpart.

Table .12Independent Samples Test According to the evaluation of services

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Administrative	Equal variances assumed	10.932	.001	.583	98	.561	.91444	1.56736	-2.19594	4.02481
	Equal variances not assumed			.682	95.906	.497	.91444	1.34150	-1.74845	3.57732
Technology	Equal variances assumed	2.145	.146	.921	98	.359	1.51337	1.64381	-1.74871	4.77545

	Equal variances not assumed			1.017	86.671	.312	1.51337	1.48851	-	4.47211
Electronic tourism	Equal variances assumed	16.362	.000	.819	98	.415	2.42781	2.96369	-	8.30916
	Equal variances not assumed			.986	97.934	.327	2.42781	2.46293	-	7.31546

From the table it is clear that there are no statistically significant differences for the companies' responses according to whether or not there is an evaluation of services, as the value of T 0,583 - 0.921 - 0.819 and all of them are statistically insignificant values, and this needs to increase awareness of the consumer in its main role and enhance the evaluation culture For the services provided so that the institutions work on feedback in developing the services provided

- Secondly: an analysis and interpretation of demographic characteristics

figure.4 according to the study sample (beneficiaries of tourist companies)

It is clear from the fees that the individuals of the sample at 1.2% ranged from less than 20 years and above 60 years, while 55.8% ranged between 20 to 40 years, while 41.8% ranged between 40 to 59 years, and therefore we conclude that the majority of the respondents at a rate of 97.6% are between the ages of 20 to 60, and this shows that the majority of the study participants own the decision regarding interest in digital tourism. It shows the presence of a high level of tourism awareness, as it showed that 72.7% of respondents work in the government sector,

Figure.5 which confirms the effect of the rate of stability of the income level on tourism activity.

The results showed that the majority of the respondents participating in the study, at a rate of 78.2%, deal with electronic companies and stores, which indicates the trend of members of the Saudi community with a high degree towards benefiting from electronic tourism companies and electronic stores, as the study determined the goals of dealing with those electronic stores and companies, the results have shown The vast majority of individuals in the sample deal with stores and electronic companies for all purposes, from purchasing products, entertainment, cruises, restaurants, car rental, and hotel reservations, at a rate of 65.5%. The study also showed that the average monthly income of individuals in the study sample ranged from less than 2000 riyal per month to the top from 10,000 riyal per month,

Figure.6 The largest percentage of those whose income ranged from more than 10,000 was 41.2%.

The study showed the responses of the sample members about the types of companies that are dealt with via the internet. The results showed that the majority of the sample members deal with both local and international companies with a percentage of 67.3%, followed by local stores by 24.8%, and this indicates a high degree of confidence in the global and internal stores. Equally, the study also showed that the average annual use of individuals in the sample of companies and electronic stores to three or more times a year by 45.5%, and the study also showed that the factors that help in selecting companies and stores excluding others at 37.6% believe that all the factors mentioned Of the after-sales services, offers, and ease of delivery, previous experiences are all important factors that help in creating trust between the beneficiary and the company, followed by a ratio of 29.1%..

Figure.7 They preferred that the main factor behind dealing with companies and stores be the offers that the company provides

The study showed that the majority of the sample individuals, at a rate of 35.2%, prefer to deal with tourist companies through credit cards, while 29.7% prefer an electronic payment mechanism, and therefore it is clear that most of the beneficiaries use credit cards for shopping and electronic tourism, and the study also showed that the average monthly spending on tourism And electronic shopping at 52.1% did not exceed 500 riyals per month, as it becomes clear that the rate of dealing with companies electronically covers most of the family needs at 70.9% of the responses of respondents, and this is considered an encouraging factor to expand digitally with tourism companies and stores.

Table .13ANOVA TESTAccording to the educational qualification of the head of the family and its relationship to individuals 'responses to the impact of digital technology on tourism and digital shopping:

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Axis 1	Between Groups	1102.109	3	367.370	6.346	.000
	Within Groups	28425.237	491	57.893		
	Total	29527.345	494			
Axis 2	Between Groups	1067.085	3	355.695	8.309	.000
	Within Groups	21018.624	491	42.808		
	Total	22085.709	494			

It is clear from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences at the level of 0.001 between the averages of individuals responses towards the first axis items, the consumer's interaction with electronic tourism, as the value of P6,346 is greater than its tabular counterparty in favor of university education, where the average scores of their responses reached 49.000 which is the highest compared to their peers, while there are statistically significant differences at the level of 0.001 between the averages of individuals responses towards the items of the second axis e-marketing in favor of university and secondary education alike where the value of the averages of their response scores 8,41 – 79,41 respectively.

Table .14.ANOVA TESTAccording to the employer of the head of the family and his relationship with individual responses to the impact of digital technology on tourism and digital shopping:

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Axis 1	Between Groups	408.747	2	204.373	3.453	.032
	Within Groups	29118.599	492	59.184		
	Total	29527.345	494			
Axis 2	Between Groups	406.251	2	203.126	4.610	.010
	Within Groups	21679.458	492	44.064		
	Total	22085.709	494			

It is clear from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences at the level of 0.05 between the averages of individuals responses towards the items of the first axis e-tourism in favor of working in the private sector of the head of the family where the average degrees of their responses reached 44,294 which is the highest compared to their counterparts, while there are differences of statistical significance At the level of significance 0.01 between the averages of individuals responses towards the second axis items (e-marketing) in favor of self-employment, where the value of the averages of the degrees of their responses reached 42.89

Third: Table.15 ANOVA TEST According to the purpose of the tourist use:

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Axis 1	Between Groups	653.516	6	108.919	1.841	.089
	Within Groups	28873.830	488	59.168		
	Total	29527.345	494			
Axis 2	Between Groups	737.433	6	122.905	2.809	.011
	Within Groups	21348.277	488	43.746		
	Total	22085.709	494			

It is clear from the previous table that there are no statistically significant differences between the averages of individuals responses towards the items of the first axis e-tourism for any purpose of digital tourism purposes, while there are statistically significant differences at the level of 0.01 between the averages of individuals responses to the items of the second axis in favor of tourism trips Where the value of averages Their response scores are 48.5

Table.16 ANOVA TEST According to the types of stores and companies:

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Axis 1	Between Groups	569.997	2	284.999	4.842	.008
	Within Groups	28957.348	492	58.856		
	Total	29527.345	494			
Axis 2	Between Groups	187.604	2	93.802	2.108	.123
	Within Groups	21898.105	492	44.508		
	Total	22085.709	494			

It is clear from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences at the level of 0.01 between the averages of individuals' responses towards the first axis items of electronic tourism in favor of dealing with international companies where the average scores of their responses reached 45,923 which is the highest compared to their peers, while there are no statistically significant differences between Average responses of individuals towards the second axis items of e-marketing for any type of company.

Fifth: (Table No.17) ANOVA TEST According to the annual use rate:

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Axis 1	Between Groups	1033.640	2	516.820	8.924	.000
	Within Groups	28493.705	492	57.914		
	Total	29527.345	494			
Axis 2	Between Groups	513.229	2	256.615	5.853	.003
	Within Groups	21572.480	492	43.847		
	Total	22085.709	494			

It is clear from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences at the level of 0.001 between the averages of individuals responses towards the items of the first axis of electronic tourism in favor of the use rate twice a year, where the average degrees of their responses reached 44,825 which is the highest compared to their counterparts, while there are statistically significant differences when Significant level of 0.01 between the individuals responses averages towards the second axis items in favor of the rate of use twice annually, where the average value of their response scores reached 42,250

Table 18 ANOVA TEST Depending on the factors for choosing the company:

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Axis 1	Between Groups	879.566	5	175.913	3.003	.011

	Within Groups	28647.780	489	58.584		
	Total	29527.345	494			
Axis 2	Between Groups	1399.610	5	279.922	6.617	.000
	Within Groups	20686.099	489	42.303		
	Total	22085.709	494			

It is clear from the previous table that there are no statistically significant differences between the averages of individuals' responses towards the items of the first axis e-tourism for companies' selection factors, while there are statistically significant differences at the level of 0.001 between the averages of individuals' responses to the items of the second axis for all factors necessary to select companies where Averages value their response scores are 44.00

Table .19 **ANOVA TEST** According to the payment systems:

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Axis 1	Between Groups	2460.363	4	615.091	11.135	.000
	Within Groups	27066.982	490	55.239		
	Total	29527.345	494			
Axis 2	Between Groups	957.362	4	239.341	5.551	.000
	Within Groups	21128.347	490	43.119		
	Total	22085.709	494			

It is clear from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences at the level of 0.001 between the averages of individuals' responses towards the first axis items of electronic tourism in favor of the electronic card payment system, where the average scores of their responses reached 42,534 which is the highest compared to their counterparts, and there are statistically significant differences when Significant level of 0.001 between the averages of individuals' responses towards the second axis items in favor of all available payment methods, where the average value of their response scores reached 42,8000

Table. 20 **Correlations** According to age, income and size of spending.

		age	income	size of spending	Axis 1	Axis 2
age	Pearson Correlation	2	.363**	.075	-.210**	-.175**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.095	.000	.000
	N	495	495	492	495	495
income	Pearson Correlation	.363**	1	.110*	-.318**	-.399**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.015	.000	.000
	N	495	495	492	495	495
size of spending	Pearson Correlation	.075	.110*	1	.114*	-.028
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.095	.015		.011	.539
	N	492	492	492	492	492
Axis 1	Pearson Correlation	-.210**	-.318**	.114*	1	.700**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.011		.000
	N	495	495	492	495	495
Axis 2	Pearson Correlation	-.175**	-.399**	-.028	.700**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.539	.000	
	N	495	495	492	495	495

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

It is clear that there is a statistically significant inverse correlation relationship at the level of significance 0.01 between age and the first and second axis so that the greater the age the greater the interaction with digital tourism and electronic marketing, there is also an inverse relationship between income and the two axes items at the level of significance 0.01, while there is a direct relationship Between the volume of spending and the use of digital tourism at the level of significance 0.05, meaning that the greater the amount of spending, the greater the rate of use of digital tourism, while there is no correlation between the volume of spending and e-marketing

Table ..21Independent Samples Test Depending on dealing with stores and companies.

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Axis 1	Equal variances assumed	1.943	.164	1.127	493	.260	.94832	.84113	-.70433	2.60097
	Equal variances not assumed			1.181	183.377	.239	.94832	.80329	-.63656	2.53320
Axis 2	Equal variances assumed	.073	.787	.836	493	.404	.60853	.72788	-.82160	2.03866
	Equal variances not assumed			.869	181.170	.386	.60853	.70062	-.77391	1.99096

From the previous table, it is clear that there are no statistically significant differences in the responses of heads of households, according to the mechanism of dealing with stores and companies.

Table.22Independent Samples Test According to the dealings with stores and companies, including family members:

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means
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	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Axis 1 Equal variances assumed	.027	.869	2.931	493	.004	2.22543	.75929	.73359	3.71726
Equal variances not assumed			2.802	242.331	.005	2.22543	.79435	.66071	3.79014
Axis 2 Equal variances assumed	.955	.329	.007	493	.994	.00481	.66237	-1.29661	1.30622
Equal variances not assumed			.007	271.366	.994	.00481	.65645	-1.28757	1.29718

From the previous table, it is clear that there are no statistically significant differences in the responses of heads of families according to the mechanism of dealing with stores and companies.

Conclusion:

With regard to companies:

The study showed that one of the most important challenges of the transformation of digital tourism is the lack of expertise for tourism companies in this field and companies' fear of that transformation

There is no difference between corporate tourism transactions depending on the location of the company and the culture of the surrounding community within the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

It became clear that the newly established companies keep pace with the modern technological development in the field of tourism more than companies with great experience that always maintain the approach taken from the start

Recreational activities have a positive effect that attracts the Saudi consumer in choosing the company

Lack of Saudi consumer awareness of the need for feedback and evaluation of dealings with tourism companies after services, With regard to Saudi families:

The study showed that one of the most important challenges of the transformation of digital tourism is the length and complexity of government procedures, as well as the lack of experience in this field and the concerns of some of the transformation

The study indicated that there is a qualified segment of the audience members who are participating in the study qualified in terms of (age, education) to take the right decisions regarding tourism and e-shopping, i.e., have the decision to shop and tourism online.

The results of the study revealed that the majority of the participating public prefers to deal with international stores, and this needs to support confidence in the market and the local companies of the consumer.

The results of the study indicated that there is a need to purchase many products and services via the Internet from electronic stores, especially tourism and leisure services. The results also indicated that all factors that drive the public to deal with companies are the quality of the company representative and this needs to support the mechanisms of technical communication between companies and consumers and rely on the means of communication and confirm confidence in them instead of the delegate

The results showed that the majority of individuals shopping believe that they have the ability to master online shopping. This shows that there are very good indicators among the general market of shoppers for using the electronic shopping and tourism websites. The results also showed that most individuals have credit cards to pay electronically.

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References

- A. Kudeshia, A.K. Jagannatham, (2014). "Optimal viterbi based total variation sequence detectionTVSD for robust image/video decoding in wireless sensor networks", IEEE Signal Processing Letters, vol. 21, pp. 722-7261.
- Abdulsahib, G. M., & Khalaf, O. I. (2018). Comparison and Evaluation of Cloud Processing Models in Cloud-Based Networks. International Journal of Simulation--Systems, Science & Technology, 19(5).
- Ayman Dawood Salman1, Osamah Ibrahim Khalaf and Ghaida Muttashar Abdulsahib, 2019. An adaptive intelligent alarm system for wireless sensor network. Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, Vol. 15, No. 1, July 2019, pp. 142~147

- Alhayani, B. and Abdallah, A.A. (2020), "Manufacturing intelligent Corvus corone module for a secured two way image transmission under WSN", *Engineering Computations*, Vol. 37 No. 9, pp. 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EC-02-2020-0107>.
- B. AlHayani, H. Ilhan,(2017). "Hyper spectral image classification using dimensionality reduction techniques",*International Journal of Innovative Research in Electrical, Electronics, Instrumentation and Control Engineering*,, vol.5, pp.71-74.
- B. Alhayani, Milind Rane. (2014). "face recognition system by image processing" *International journal of electronics and communication engineering & technology (IJCIET)*,vol.5, no.5, pp. 80–90.
- B. Al-Hayani, H. Ilhan. (2020)"Visual Sensor Intelligent Module Based Image Transmission in Industrial Manufacturing for Monitoring and Manipulation problems,"*Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, vol.4,pp.1-14..
- S. Heng, C. So-In, and T.G. Nguyen, (2017)."Distributed image compression architecture over wireless multimedia sensor networks," *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, vol., pp. 1530-8669.
- S. Mukhopadhyay, C. Schurgers, D. Panigrahi and S. Dey,(2015). "Model-Based techniques for data reliability in wireless sensor networks," in *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 528-543.
- S. Xu, C. Li, F. Li, and S. Zhang, (2012). "An improved sliding window algorithm for ECC multiplication," *World Automation Congress*, , pp. 335-338..
- T. Ma, M. Hempel, K. Hua, D. Peng and H. Sharif,(2010,) "A novel cooperative image transmission scheme in Wireless Sensor Networks," *IEEE Local Computer Network Conference*, Denver, CO, pp. 240-243
- A. Kudeshia, A.K. Jagannatham, (2014). "Optimal viterbi based total variation sequence detectionTVSD for robust image/video decoding in wireless sensor networks", *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 21, pp. 722-7261.
- Alhayani B., H. Ilhan.(2020). "Image transmission over decode and forward based cooperative wireless multimedia sensor networks for Rayleigh fading channels in medical internet of things (MIoT) for remote health-care and health communication monitoring," *Journal of Medical Imaging And Health Informatics*, vol. 10, pp. 160-168.
- Alhayani B.,H.Ilhan. (2020). Efficient cooperative image transmission in one-Way mult-hop sensor network," *International Journal of Electrical Engineering Education*, vol.57, no.2, pp.321-339.
- Alhayani B., H. Ilhan.(2020). "Image transmission over decode and forward based cooperative wireless multimedia sensor networks for Rayleigh fading channels in medical internet of things (MIoT) for remote health-care and health communication monitoring," *Journal of Medical Imaging And Health Informatics*, vol. 10, pp. 160-168.
- N. Ahmed, T. Natarajan and K. R. Rao,(1974). "Discrete cosine transform," in *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, "vol. C-23, no. 1, pp. 90-93.
- R. Krishna, C. V. M. S. Teja, S. Renuga Devi and V. Thanikaiselvan, (2018)."A Chaos Based Image Encryption Using Tinkerbell Map Functions," *Second International Conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology*, Coimbatore, , pp..578-582.
- S. Heng, C. So-In, and T.G. Nguyen, (2017)."Distributed image compression architecture over wireless multimedia sensor networks," *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, vol., pp. 1530-8669.
- S. Mukhopadhyay, C. Schurgers, D. Panigrahi and S. Dey,(2015). "Model-Based techniques for data reliability in wireless sensor networks," in *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 528-543.
- S. Xu, C. Li, F. Li, and S. Zhang, (2012). "An improved sliding window algorithm for ECC multiplication," *World Automation Congress*, , pp. 335-338..
- T. Ma, M. Hempel, K. Hua, D. Peng and H. Sharif,(2010,) "A novel cooperative image transmission scheme in Wireless Sensor Networks," *IEEE Local Computer Network Conference*, Denver, CO, pp. 240-243.

Author Information

Dr. Haifa Hammoud Al-Shammari1

Assistant professor - Department of Social Sciences -
University of ha'il, Hail,55211,KSA

Dr. Nancy Abdel-Maboad El-Sawy

Assistant professor-Department of Fine Arts -
University of ha'il, Hail,55211,KSA
